

IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING IN HIGHER EDUCATION.

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Today, learning foreign languages is one of the most important requirements of our time. With this in mind, the article discusses the need to improve the quality of foreign language teaching in higher education, the use of various modern methods in the process, and more.

ABSTRACT

One of the most pressing issues in education is to reform the system of foreign language teaching, the application of advanced teaching methods in the teaching process using modern pedagogical and information and communication technologies. With the rapid development of information and communication technologies, which is one of the peculiarities of our time, special attention is paid to a new approach to the educational process and its organization, using its potential. The XXI century is the age of high technologies, and our modern youth is not only in line with the spirit of the times, but also in line with the development of the electronic world. Therefore, it requires a different approach to the process of educating the younger generation. The role of the teacher in the classroom is also changing. The teacher is now mainly a facilitator. It is time for teachers who want to keep pace with the times to be ready to bring any part of the lesson to life through information and communication technologies.

Every state that chooses rapid development and progress emphasizes, first, the upbringing of the younger generation as perfect and mature people in all respects. It is worth noting that the education system has a special role to play in achieving this goal.

In order to increase the quality and efficiency of higher education institutions, it is necessary to introduce international standards for assessing the quality of education and training. It is important to assess not only the knowledge of students, but also the quality of education and training. Naturally, this task is related to

the material and technical base of the educational institution, personnel knowledge and potential, the use of modern information and communication and pedagogical technologies. At the same time, those engaged in pedagogical activity should have high moral qualities. Only then will it be possible to think about the quality of students' knowledge and education.

Main part

Quality of education - determines the state and outcome of the educational process in society, as well as the formation and development of professional, domestic and civic competence of the individual in

accordance with the needs and requirements of society. Indicators that describe various aspects of the educational activity of the educational institution assess the quality of education. These indicators include the content of education, forms and methods of teaching, material and technical base, staffing, etc., which ensure the development of students' competencies. In addition, the quality of education is a set of knowledge required in specific conditions, which is necessary to improve the quality of personal life and use it to achieve a specific goal.

The quality of education in higher education is a multifaceted, multi-level concept related to the indicators, goals and objectives of the education model, as well as specific standards of the education system, educational institutions, curricula and disciplines.

The focus in the learning process is the teacher. Therefore, the organization of the quality of education begins with the correct formation of the teaching staff. The question arises: how can we determine the quality of a teacher? The teacher not only imparts knowledge to the students, he also plays an important role in shaping the personality, worldview and spirituality of the future staff. Therefore, teacher quality is a complex concept that can mainly include:

- have a high level of knowledge and experience in a specific field of science and practice;
- Ability and desire to engage in teaching activities;
- Observation - rapid recognition of abilities and individual characteristics of students;
- Ability to communicate with external and internal environment;

- Recognition, position in their field;
- Activity in the field of research;
- The existence of a scientific school, etc.

The system of retraining and advanced training also plays an important role in ensuring the quality and effectiveness of education. It is important to improve the scientific potential of teachers working in this system, to improve the quality of teaching, to create opportunities for them to engage in research, to implement measures aimed at external evaluation of teachers.

In the process of training and retraining of teachers, it is necessary to ensure continuity and continuity between the public education and higher education systems, to inform teachers about innovations in teaching methods, the theory of education and upbringing, reforms in higher education, best international practices.

We have concluded that the quality of education in our country is determined primarily by the quality, level and qualifications of knowledge holders and distributors. Knowledge holders are the teaching staff of a particular university and their scientific potential. They educate students using a variety of pedagogical technologies and innovative methods. Therefore, the modernity of knowledge transfer technology, the level of mastery of students by it, the robustness and validity of the acquired knowledge also play an important role. The graduate is also required to know how much knowledge is needed or needed after employment in manufacturing. This, in turn, necessitates the development of integration of education and production. Scientific and technological progress is creating new

means and tools of labor. Therefore, in order to introduce modern technologies and technical means into production, to organize the production of competitive products in line with the world market, the graduate is required to constantly learn new innovative technologies and techniques in their work, that is, to acquire knowledge. As a result, in addition to imparting knowledge to the student, it is necessary to form and develop his ability to learn independently.

It is more effective than traditional methods of teaching, such as interactive methods of explanation, demonstration and use of tools, which are an important factor in the formation of students as individuals, the development of personal abilities, creative independence.

The differences between interactive learning and traditional learning can be seen in:

- When teaching the subjects in the curriculum, it is necessary to take into account the topics on which it is advisable to organize interactive lessons. This involves the use of interactive or traditional types of activities that ensure that the objectives of each session are fully achieved.

- For the interactive lesson to be effective, it is important to ensure that students know the basic concepts and background information on the topic before the new lesson.

- It is important to keep in mind that interactive learning takes more time for students to work independently than traditional learning.

The interactive lesson is organized in such a way that no student is left out in the process, that is, they have the opportunity to openly express what they

see, know and think. When students work together, they have the opportunity to make a personal contribution to the content of the topic. There is a process of exchanging knowledge, ideas, ideas. Such situations provide mutual sincerity, encourage the acquisition and acquisition of new knowledge, in the process of which support each other and develop friendly relations. This is of great educational importance.

In short, interactive learning allows you to solve several problems at once. Most importantly, it develops students' communication skills and abilities, helps to establish emotional connections between students, teaches them to work in a team, to listen to the opinions of their peers.

At the same time, practice shows that the use of interactive methods in the classroom eliminates the nervous tension of students, allows them to change the form of activity, to focus on the main issues of the lesson.

The main goal of the educational process is to train highly qualified, well-versed specialists in all areas of science. Therefore, it is important to use modern information technology tools in the study of modern foreign languages. Direct use of modern teaching aids, language labs, multimedia, specially programmed topics, multilingual electronic dictionaries in foreign language lessons is advisable.

Computer technology has a wide range of possibilities, especially for learning languages using the Internet. They are as follows:

- to actively use in practice the knowledge and skills acquired in oral communication in a foreign language, to learn to use the acquired language materials not only in his speech, but also in

understanding the speech of the interlocutor, whom he met on the Internet;

- to develop the ability to adapt the acquired speech knowledge to the changing situations of the relationship;

- to create a strong, immediate motivation and motivation to approach the truth in relation to the organization of the conversation, the study of speech, which takes place in the form of informal communication;

- overcoming psychological barriers, in particular, the fear of speaking a foreign language and making mistakes, the loss of the barrier and the feeling of internal and external tension and embarrassment;

Conclusion

Today, one of the main requirements for higher professional skills is a perfect knowledge of foreign languages. It is no coincidence that special attention is

paid to the study of English, which is one of the leading languages of international communication. Teaching English in the education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan is rising to a new level of quality on the basis of a scientific approach, the introduction of new information and communication technologies that can meet the requirements of the time. As the study of foreign languages is a modern requirement, it is important for scientists and experts to develop new methods of language learning and recommend it to the younger generation.

From the above, it can be concluded that the importance of an innovative approach to improving the quality of education, the harmonization of the structure, structure and content of educational literature with international requirements should be considered as an important factor.

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